

The discovery that global warming is accelerating

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Abstract.

In this study, we are going to review,

five global warming datasets by their pairs of graphs, in logical order:

- (1) The Global Carbon Budget (GCB) Annual World carbon dioxide emissions.
- (2) The NOAA Global Monitoring Laboratory (GML) Annual increase in atmospheric CO₂.
- (3) The NASA CERES Earth's cumulative radiant heat energy absorption anomaly.
- (4) The Met Office Hadley Centre HadCRUT5 Global surface air temperature anomaly.
- (5) The Met Office Hadley Centre HadSST4 Global sea surface temperature anomaly.

(1) is the cause of (2), which is the cause of (3), which is the cause of (4) and (5).

The cause of (1) is the root cause of global warming.

For each of the five pairs of graphs, we are going to demonstrate:

(A) The annual increments data graph, may be compared with an arithmetic sequence, which is either, a simple linear regression, or an estimated straight line of best fit, with a constant upward gradient.

(B) The resulting annually cumulative data graph, may be compared with the arithmetic series and the quadratic time integral, of the arithmetic sequence, which are upwards curves of best fit, which demonstrate acceleration, in all five cases.

With the evidence,

that all five cases are accelerating phenomena, we demonstrate causality,

that (1) is the directly proportionally accelerating root cause of (2),

which is the directly proportional accelerating root cause of (3),

which is the directly proportional accelerating root causes of (4) and (5).

GCB = The Global Carbon Budget.

NOAA = The USA National Oceanographic and Atmospheric Administration.

NASA = The USA National Aerospace and Space Administration.

CERES = 'The Clouds and The Earth's Radiant Energy System' Earth observation satellite.

MOHC = The UK Met Office Hadley Centre.

(1.1) Introduction.

Hello to you, all my readers, my name is Michael Jenkins,
I am only one of the UK home population, with UK schools O levels and A levels,
in English and maths and science, I am not at university, I am not an academic researcher,
I only live a home-life, and I am one of the UK BBC Radio 4 listener population.
I feel I that am responsible, and that there is an urgent need to write this article.
My spreadsheet data for this article is available at the above citable DOI link.
I am going to work for the time period 1959 – 2025.
Please respect that I may have made a scientific discovery¹,
so that I may earn the right to scientific priority².
You, all my readers, may take this discovery forward, in any responsible caring way,
all I ask is, that you all may acknowledge me, simply by my name, Michael Jenkins, please.

I am working in LibreOffice Writer³ and LibreOffice Calc⁴,
and I do all my project work, in Xubuntu Linux 24.04 LTS⁵, all of which I love.
Please accept my use of references to Wikipedia educational knowledge articles.

I deeply profoundly care, for our perfect beautiful peaceful planet Earth,
with its beautiful blue sky, and all beautiful green plant life,
and all beautiful conscious animal life, and all beautiful conscious human life,
and our whole architecture for civilisation.

I deeply profoundly care,
about the public understanding of global warming and climate change,
and the very real need to establish true climate mitigation,
in us, our whole world population, which would be, world population climate action,
which would be, us, our whole world population, actually caring,
and actually choosing, to use, less or much less, carbon combustion energy, every day.

Recently, in the last month, I began to learn about global warming,
in a new way to me, by searching and reading and learning online and in Wikipedia,
about, the meaning of the greenhouse effect⁶,
which is caused by accumulating greenhouse gases in our finite air atmosphere,
so that, incoming solar shortwave infrared radiant heat energy⁷,
which is absorbed by the Earth's land and oceans,
which is then radiated upwards as outgoing longwave infrared radiant heat energy⁸,
is, then, absorbed by the greenhouse gases in our finite air atmosphere,
which causes the Earth's cumulative radiant heat energy absorption anomaly (ECRHEAA)⁹,
in The Earth's energy budget¹⁰, which is also known as, the Earth's energy imbalance (EEI).
The greenhouse gases then radiate more longwave infrared in all directions.
All of which then causes the atmosphere¹¹ and the land and the oceans¹² to warm,
which is what global warming is.
Global warming is the root cause of all distressing adverse climate change,¹³
and all the distressing adverse effects of climate change¹⁴.

(1.2) Dedication.

This article is dedicated to the faithful lifetimes of work,
of these five sets of global warming scientists,
whose decades of data I use, to demonstrate, especially for them,
that global warming is accelerating:

(1) Professor Pierre Friedlingstein FRS¹⁵ et al, including Professor Corinne Le Quéré CBE FRS¹⁶, at The Global Carbon Budget¹⁷ at the University of Exeter, who worked to produce their Global Carbon Budget 2024¹⁸. Their data that I use, is their measurements for annual world fossil fuel carbon emissions¹⁹, for 1959 – 2024, in section (2.1).

(2) Dr Xin Lan²⁰ and Dr Pieter Tans²¹ and KW Thoning, at The USA NOAA Global Monitoring Laboratory (GML)²². Their data that I use, is their measurements, for, annual incremental global atmospheric carbon dioxide²³, for 1959 to 2024, in section (2.2).

(3) Dr Norman Loeb²⁴ et al. NASA CERES²⁵ Principal Investigator. Their data is, is The NASA CERES Earth's cumulative radiant heat energy absorption anomaly, (ECRHEAA)²⁶, for 2001 to 2023, in section (2.3).

(4) Dr Colin Morice²⁷ et al. The UK Met Office Hadley Centre²⁸ (MOHC). Their data that I use, is The MOHC HadCRUT5 Global surface air temperature (GSAT)²⁹, for 1959 – 2025, in section (2.4).

(5) Dr John Kennedy³⁰ et al, including Dr Caroline Sandford. The UK Met Office Hadley Centre (MOHC). Their data that I use, is The MOHC HadSST4 Global sea surface temperature (GSST)³¹, for 1959 – 2025, in section (2.5)

(1.3) Revision: The Science of Radiant Heat Energy and Kinetic Heat Energy.

We need to remember and understand, that the temperature³² of matter, consisting of atoms and molecules, is a measure of its heat energy content, which is atomic and molecular vibration³³, which is a form of kinetic energy³⁴.

So, the kinetic heat energy content of matter, gives that matter, its temperature. So, in a sense, the kinetic heat energy content of a material, causes its temperature. All matter with heat content, radiates heat as electromagnetic infrared thermal radiation^{35 36}, including The Sun.

These are two kinds of heat, atomic molecular vibrational kinetic heat energy, which is material, and electromagnetic infrared radiant heat energy, which is immaterial, which may pass through space.

(1.3.1) The term heat³⁷, actually means, the transfer of heat³⁸, between two places with different temperatures.

There are only three kinds of heat energy transfer:

- (1) Infrared radiant heat energy³⁹ transfer, by electromagnetic infrared thermal radiation⁴⁰, passing through space, which may be absorbed by matter, which will increase its atomic molecular vibration, so, radiant heat energy is photons, which are not matter, as photons have no rest mass.
- (2) Heat energy transfer by conduction⁴¹, in matter, through matter, which is the transfer of atomic molecular vibration through matter.
- (3) Matter may transfer heat by thermal convection⁴², by matter moving through space.

(1.3.2) We need to remember and understand, that the origin of Global Warming is:
(1) The absorption of outgoing longwave infrared radiant heat energy, from The Earth, which is photons, by greenhouse gases, in our finite air atmosphere, which are matter, which increases their molecular vibration kinetic heat energy, which then warms the atmosphere, which is one part the greenhouse effect.
(2) The greenhouse gas molecules then re-radiate their kinetic heat energy, as longwave infrared radiant heat energy, in all directions, including back to The Earth's land and oceans, which is the second part of the greenhouse effect.
Understanding this may explain what is happening, in extreme heat, and heat domes⁴³.

We need to remember and understand, that all this infrared radiant heat energy, is electromagnetic radiation, which radiates, travels, through space, independently of the matter which it warms, all of which is expressed in The Earth's energy budget diagrams⁴⁴.

When infrared radiant heat energy interacts with matter, which it warms, it is causing an increase in that matter's atomic molecular kinetic heat energy content, which causes an increase in that matter's temperature.

Energy, has several distinct forms⁴⁵, which should always be specified, for examples: light energy, heat energy, kinetic energy, electric energy, mechanical energy, chemical energy, gravitational potential energy, stored electric energy.

One form of energy may transform⁴⁶ into another form of energy, and the law of conservation of energy⁴⁷ applies, to all energy and to all energy transformations.

Incoming solar shortwave infrared radiant heat energy, and outgoing longwave infrared radiant heat energy, are pure electromagnetic radiant heat energy phenomena, which are being measured, by the NASA Terra Earth Observation Satellite with its CERES⁴⁸ instruments.

The NASA Terra CERES Earth observation satellite, is able to measure, the Earth's reflected shortwave radiant heat energy, and the Earth's outgoing longwave radiant heat energy, and measure their difference to the known absolute incoming solar radiant heat energy⁴⁹, so that NASA Terra CERES is able to directly measure The Earth's Energy Absorption, which is the origin of global warming, which NASA CERES measure as, The Earth's cumulative radiant heat energy absorption anomaly (ECRHEAA)⁵⁰.

It is these two infrared radiant heat energies, that warm the matter of the Earth, the atmosphere and the land and the oceans, and cause the increase in their atomic molecular vibration kinetic heat energies, which is expressed by an increase in their temperatures.

The greenhouse gas absorption of outgoing longwave infrared radiant heat energy, is the origin of global warming, which is the increase of the whole material Earth's kinetic heat energy content, which is conserved, by the law of energy conservation, and is accumulating, in all the matter of the Earth, this is what the phenomenon of global warming is, which then causes the increase in global surface air temperature, and global sea surface temperature.

We would expect, that when the pure constant infrared interacts with matter, there is an element of randomness, which may produce natural fluctuations.

In section (2.3), We can see natural fluctuations in The NASA CERES figures 5, 6, 7, 8.

In sections (2.4) and (2.5), we can see even more natural fluctuations, for the Met Office HadCRUT5 global surface air temperature (GSAT), in figures 9 and 10, and the Met Office HadSST global sea surface temperature (GSST), in figures 11 and 12.

(1.4) The insights and the mathematics, that lead to the discovery that global warming is accelerating.

Here we are going to look at, this specific application of this specific UK schools A level maths subject, of the summation⁵¹ of sequences⁵² of numbers, to produce series⁵³ (plural) of numbers.

The sequences and their summation series, that we are going to look at, are natural sequences with their natural series, which are the five global warming datasets, that I have named above, which we will do in comparison to arithmetic sequences with their arithmetic series. The arithmetic sequences are either, simple linear regression, or estimated line of best fit,

Summation, to produce a series, is not a simple sum, it is the summation of all the earlier summations in the series.

Therefore, it is important to understand, that the natural sequence is annual increments (quantity per unit time), and its natural series is cumulative (absolute quantity).

So, the relationship between, natural sequences, in comparison to arithmetic sequences, & their summation natural series (plural), in comparison to summation arithmetic series, is like that of a time integral⁵⁴, from a linear time function⁵⁵ to a quadratic time function⁵⁶. Similarly, in the reverse direction, the relationship between, summation natural series (plural), in comparison to summation arithmetic series (plural), and, their natural sequences, in comparison to linear arithmetic sequences, is like that of a time derivative⁵⁷, from a quadratic time function, to a linear time function.

The five sets of global warning data that we are analysing, shall be in pairs, natural sequences with their summation to natural series.

We are going to compare these natural sequences and their natural series, to arithmetic sequences⁵⁸ with their summation to arithmetic series (plural), and their time integral to quadratic curves, which, mathematically, are acceleration. Therefore, we are using the arithmetic sequence and its arithmetic series, and its time integral, as the mathematical model⁵⁹, for comparison, to the natural sequence and its natural series.

The first insight is to recognise the question, what form is the data in ? Is it, the annual increments (quantity per unit time) natural sequence, or, is it the annually cumulative (quantity) natural series ? For each form, we then need to calculate the other form in the spreadsheet data, in order to create the pair of data, from which we create the pairs of graphs.

(1.4.1) For Professor Pierre Friedlingstein FRS et al, in section (2.1), their data is, the natural sequence, annual world carbon emissions (GT(C)/y).
(1) We need to calculate, annual world carbon dioxide emissions (Gt(CO₂)/y).
(2) The second insight, is, we need to recognise, that annual world carbon dioxide emissions, accumulate into our finite air atmosphere, so their effect is cumulative, so, their summation is the natural series, which is the annually cumulative carbon dioxide emissions (Gt(CO₂)), as an anomaly⁶⁰, zeroed at 1959.

(1.4.2) For Dr Xin Lan and Dr Pieter Tans and KW Thoning, in section (2.2).
(1) Their data, is the natural sequence, of annual increment in global atmospheric carbon dioxide (ppm(mol(CO₂)/mol(Air))/y).
(2) The third insight, is, we need to recognise, that the annual increments in global atmospheric carbon dioxide, accumulate in our finite air atmosphere, so the phenomenon is cumulative, so, their summation, is the natural series, annually cumulative atmospheric carbon dioxide (ppm(mol(CO₂)/mol(Air))), as an anomaly, zeroed at 1959.

(1.4.3) For Dr Norman Loeb et al, in section (2.3).
(1) The fourth insight, is we need to recognise, that their data, is the natural series, which is the Earth's cumulative radiant heat energy absorption anomaly (ECRHEAA), in Zetta Joules (ZJ) (10²¹ Joules), zeroed at 2001.
(2) Therefore, we need to calculate, the natural sequence, the Earth's annual radiant heat energy absorption (EARHEA) (ZJ/y).

(1.4.4) For Dr Colin Morice et al, and Dr John Kennedy et al, in sections (2.4) and (2.5).
(1) The fifth insight, is we need to recognise, that their data, HadCRUT5 global surface air temperature (C), and HadSST4 global sea surface temperature (C), are the natural series,
(2) So, we need to calculate the natural sequences, which are, the annual change in global surface air temperature (C/y). and the annual change in global sea surface air temperature (C/y).

This sixth insight is that for each dataset, we are compiling the data, as a pair of data, the natural sequence with its summation to its natural series.

(1.4.5) The seventh insight, is to recognise, that, initially, when we look at all these pairs of data as graphs, over many years, we can see:
(1) The five natural sequences demonstrate general upward trends, for which we shall carry out, simple linear regression⁶¹, in sections (2.1)(2.2)(2.3), and estimated straight lines of best fit, in sections (2.4)(2.5), which are arithmetic sequences.
(2) The five natural series (plural) demonstrate general increasing upward trends, which we shall compare with, the arithmetic series (plural) of the arithmetic sequences, and, the quadratic time integrals of the arithmetic sequences, which are quadratic curves of best fit.
(3) Thereby, we shall demonstrate, that each natural series, can be compared to an accelerating arithmetic series model, and an accelerating time integral model, therefore, we shall demonstrate, that the trend in each natural series is long-term acceleration.

(1.4.6) The eighth insight, is we need to recognise:

(1) The root cause of global warming, is the huge annual magnitude, of our world population demand for carbon combustion energy,

which is a natural sequence, which is the directly proportional linear root cause of:

(2) The huge annual magnitude of our world carbon dioxide emissions, into our finite air atmosphere,

which, as we have seen, because of its annually cumulative effect,

its result is, we shall see, that it is the directly proportional accelerating root cause of:

(3) Accelerating annually cumulative world carbon dioxide emissions, into Our Finite Air Atmosphere,

which are the directly proportional accelerating root cause of:

(4) Accelerating annually cumulative atmospheric carbon dioxide,

which is the directly proportional accelerating root cause of:

(5) The accelerating Earth's cumulative radiant heat energy absorption anomaly, (ECRHEAA), which is the directly proportional accelerating root cause of:

(6) The accelerating trend in global surface air temperature, and the accelerating trend in global sea surface temperature.

Thereby, we shall make the discovery that global warming is accelerating.

In (1.4.6)(1)(2)(3)(4)(5)(6), the root cause of global warming, and, global warming, itself, are all directly proportionally⁶² sequentially causally⁶³ related.

I understood all these insights, all in one go, right at the beginning, before anything, which is why I have immediately urgently done all this work, and gone to all this effort to demonstrate and document everything correctly, for you all.

A proper evidence synthesis⁶⁴ report, is for politicians.

This article may be regarded as a special evidence synthesis report,

for all our world's climate scientists, and especially for, these global warming scientists,

Professor Pierre Friedlingstein et al, Dr Xin Lan, Dr Pieter Tans, KW Thoning,

Dr Norman Loeb et al, Dr Colin Morice et al, and Dr John Kennedy et al,

who have faithfully worked for so many years, to maintain making their measurements.

In addition, I wish to bring together,

Professor Pierre Friedlingstein et al, Dr Xin Lan, Dr Pieter Tans, KW Thoning,

Dr Norman Loeb et al, Dr Colin Morice et al, and Dr John Kennedy et al,

as specialist global warming scientists, in new friendships with each other,

and in new communications with each other, and in new understandings with each other,

with this discovery of this demonstration with this mathematics,

because all together, they have all been faithfully working in all their lifetimes of work,

on measuring all these sequentially causally related aspects of global warming.

(2.1) The Global Carbon Budget (GCB), the huge cumulative magnitude, of our world carbon dioxide emissions anomaly, into our finite air atmosphere, when compared to an arithmetic series and a quadratic time integral.

For a very long time, I have been aware,

of the phenomenal work of The Global Carbon Budget,

with Professor Pierre Friedlingstein FRS et al,

including Professor Corinne LeQuere CBE FRS, whom I respect immensely.

So, I turned to their global carbon budget for 2024. Very helpfully, for the same time period as The NOAA GML data, 1959 - 2022, Professor Pierre Friedlingstein FRS et al, provide the huge annual magnitude of our world carbon combustion energy emissions, into our finite air atmosphere, as elemental carbon, in giga tonnes per year, which is the equivalent, of the huge annual magnitude of our world carbon combustion energy economy.

In the LibreOffice Calc Spreadsheet, I converted this elemental carbon data, into the huge annual magnitude of our world annual carbon dioxide emissions, in giga tonnes of carbon dioxide per year.

Annual world carbon dioxide emissions are a natural sequence of annual quantities, which are steadily increasing, because our world population demand, for carbon combustion energy, is uncaringly steadily increasing, not caringly decreasing.

I worked to create figure 1, to illustrate this natural sequence, for the years, 1959 - 2025, and to illustrate its simple linear regression straight line of best fit, in comparison to the natural sequence.

The insight is, annual world carbon dioxide emissions, are emitted each year, into, our finite air atmosphere, which then accumulate, year by year, in, our finite air atmosphere, so that, year by year, their effect is cumulative.

So, we need to carry out the summation of this natural sequence, in order to learn the natural series, of the huge cumulative magnitude of our world carbon dioxide emissions, in our finite air atmosphere, due to the annual world carbon dioxide emissions, into our finite air atmosphere. We will do this, as an anomaly, relative to its zeroed value, at 1959.

For figure 2, we are going carry out the summation, of the natural sequence and the arithmetic sequence, to produce a natural series and an arithmetic series, and we are going to create the quadratic time integral of the arithmetic sequence, which we may compare.

From figure 2, we can immediately clearly see, that the natural sequence produced a natural series with an upward curve, and that the arithmetic sequence, produced an arithmetic series, and a time integral, which are quadratic curves of best fit, which do compare to the natural series, of cumulative world carbon dioxide emissions.

By mathematical definition, this time integral, which is an upward quadratic curve, is an acceleration.

Therefore, we may rationally observe, that cumulative world carbon dioxide emissions, into our finite air atmosphere, is an accelerating phenomenon.

The gradient of the arithmetic sequence, in figure 1, is the rate of acceleration of the quadratic time integral, in figure 2.

We may extrapolate from figures 1 and 2, that the rate of acceleration of the quadratic time integral, is 0.453 giga tonnes of carbon dioxide per year per year (Gt(CO₂)/y/y), which equals 453 mega tonnes of carbon dioxide per year per year (Mt(CO₂)/y/y).

(2.2) The NOAA Global Monitoring Laboratory (GML), cumulative global atmospheric carbon dioxide anomaly, when compared to an arithmetic series and a quadratic time integral.

Let us do the same analysis for cumulative global atmospheric carbon dioxide, as we did for cumulative world carbon dioxide emissions.

For a very long time, I been aware of the phenomenal work, of The NOAA Global Monitoring Laboratory's (GML), global atmospheric carbon dioxide measurements, by Dr Xin Lan, Dr Pieter Tans, and K.W. Thoning, whom I respect immensely.

Let us turn to the NOAA GML data, for the annual increments in atmospheric carbon dioxide, 1959 - 2025⁶⁵, measured in the dimensions unit, ppm(mol(CO₂)/mol(air))/y. (ppm = parts per million).

This data is a natural sequence, and we would expect natural fluctuations.

I put this data into the LibreOffice Calc Spreadsheet, to produce figure 3, I carried out simple linear regression, to create this straight line of best fit.

To produce figure 4, we already have the natural sequence, in figure 3, for which we are going to apply summation, to learn the natural series, and we are going to do: the summation of the linear arithmetic sequence, to produce its arithmetic series, and, the time integral of the arithmetic sequence, to produce an upward quadratic curve.

Yes, in figure 4, on first sight, we can clearly see, that the approximation of the arithmetic series and time integral models, to the natural series, hold true.

The time integral model, which is an upward quadratic curve, indicates accelerating cumulative atmospheric carbon dioxide.

We may deduce⁶⁶, that the GCB cumulative world carbon dioxide emissions, which we have seen in figure 2, is the directly proportional⁶⁷ accelerating root cause, of this accelerating NOAA GML cumulative atmospheric carbon dioxide, in figure 4.

The gradient of the arithmetic sequence in figure 3, is the rate of acceleration of the quadratic time integral, in figure 4.

We may extrapolate from Graphs 3 and 4, that the rate of acceleration in the quadratic time integral model, is 0.029120 ppm(mol(CO₂)/mol(Air))/y/y, which equals 29.120 ppb(mol(CO₂)/mol(Air))/y/y. (ppb = parts per billion).

(2.3) The NASA CERES Earth's cumulative radiant heat energy absorption anomaly, (ECRHEAA), when compared to an arithmetic series and a quadratic time integral.

I was learning about The Earth's energy budget, and The Earth's energy absorption, when, by a miracle, I found online, this deeply profoundly significant, figure 5.

My new understandings for the whole Earth's radiant heat energy phenomenon, helped me to understand the significance of this figure 5, which triggered my whole interest, which led to this whole discovery.

The NASA CERES Earth's radiation balance, 2001-2023.

Released, Tuesday 10 October 2023.

By The NASA Science Visualisation Studio (SVS).

Visualisations by Trent Schindler, produced by Jonathan Gleason, written by Denise Lineberry, scientific consulting by Dr Norman Loeb, all of whom I newly respect immensely.

Figure 5 illustrates a cumulative natural series.

I needed to invert the colours of figure 5, using GIMP⁶⁸, in order to produce figure 6, in order to be able to print it to A4, in order to be able to manually extrapolate the annually cumulative series data.

Figure 6. Cumulative Planetary Heat Content Anomaly of Earth, Observed by Ceres.

By The NASA Science Visualisation Studio.

(<https://svs.gsfc.nasa.gov/5173>)

Trent Schindler, Jonathan Gleason, Denise Lineberry, Dr Norman Loeb.

(<https://terra.nasa.gov/about/terra-instruments/ceres>)

Being European, I love SI units⁶⁹ and metric prefixes⁷⁰, in orders of thousands, so, to make figure 6, I changed figure 5's units from 10^{22} Joules, to Zetta Joules (ZJ), where, 1 Zetta Joule (ZJ) = 10^{21} Joules, so, 1×10^{22} Joules = 10 Zetta Joules (ZJ).

I placed figure 6, NASA CERES Earth's cumulative radiant heat energy anomaly (ECRHEAA), in an A4 pdf, which I printed, then with a ruler, I manually measured the data points, for ECRHEAA (ZJ), in millimetres, for Each Year, 2001 - 2022.

I entered this data in my LibreOffice Calc spreadsheet,

I zeroed the data on the year 2001, then, for each year, I calculated:

- (1) Earth's annual cumulative radiant heat energy absorption anomaly (ECRHEAA), in Zetta Joules (ZJ), which is a cumulative natural series,
- (2) and the annual increment, Earth's annual radiant heat energy absorption (EARHEA), in Zetta Joules per year (ZJ/y), which is its natural sequence.

I carried out simple linear regression on the natural sequence,

to produce a straight line of best fit, which is an arithmetic sequence.

I was able to produce figure 7.

Figure 7. NASA CERES. Earth's annual radiant heat energy absorption (EARHEA) (ZJ/y).

Dr Norman Loeb, Trent Schindler, Jonathan Gleason, Denise Lineberry.
NASA Science Visualisation Studio (<https://svs.gsfc.nasa.gov/5173>).

— Earth's annual radiant heat energy absorption (EARHEA) (Zetta Joules/year) (ZJ/y).
— Simple linear regression = arithmetic sequence.

Figure 7, is derived from the original NASA CERES figure 6, so, we now need to reinterpret this figure 7, back to the original NASA CERES figure 6, to produce figure 8.

The original NASA CERES figure 6, is the Earth's cumulative radiant heat energy absorption anomaly (ECRHEAA), as actually measured by The NASA Terra CERES Earth observation satellite⁷¹, which is a natural series, which is the summation of the natural sequence, of Earth's Annual Radiant Heat Energy Absorption (EARHEA), in figure 7.

For figure 8, we may now anticipate that we shall see the same phenomenon, the summation of the arithmetic sequence, in figure 7, which is the linear straight line of best fit, translates to its arithmetic series, and its quadratic time integral, which shall be upward quadratic curves of best fit, which compare to the natural series.

Figure 8. NASA CERES. Earth's cumulative radiant heat energy absorption anomaly (ECRHEAA).

Dr Norman Loeb, Trent Schindler, Jonathan Gleason, Denise Lineberry.
NASA Science Visualisation Studio (<https://svs.gsfc.nasa.gov/5173>).

- Earth's cumulative radiant heat energy absorption anomaly (ECRHEAA) (Zetta Joules) (ZJ).
- Arithmetic series summation of simple linear regression.
- Quadratic time integral of simple linear regression = constant acceleration.

Yes, in figure 8, on first sight, we can clearly see, that the comparison, of the arithmetic series and the time integral, to the natural series, hold true.

The time integral model, which is an upward quadratic curve, indicates that Earth's cumulative radiant heat energy absorption anomaly (ECRHEAA), is accelerating

We may now deduce, that the accelerating GCB cumulative world carbon dioxide emissions, in figure 2, are the directly proportional accelerating root cause of, the accelerating NOAA GML cumulative atmospheric carbon dioxide, in figure 4, which is the directly proportional accelerating root cause of, this accelerating NASA CERES ECRHEAA, in figure 8.

The gradient of the arithmetic sequence in figure 7, is the rate of acceleration of the quadratic time integral, in figure 8.

We may extrapolate from figures 7 and 8, that the rate of acceleration of the quadratic time integral, is 0.749 Zetta Joules per year per year (ZJ/y/y), which equals 749 Exa Joules per year per year (EJ/y/y). (Exa = 10^{18}).

The NASA CERES Earth's cumulative radiant heat energy absorption anomaly (ECRHEAA), is the key metric for the origin of all global warming, as the cumulative transfer of radiant heat energy to the whole Earth's kinetic heat energy, which, itself, is then the root cause, the distressing adverse annual incremental trends, of the Met Office HadCRUT5 global surface air temperature (GSAT), and the Met Office HadSST global sea surface temperature (GSST).

Clearly, the thought, the understanding, and the realisation, for this new understanding, that global warming, as measured by, The NASA CERES Earth's cumulative heat energy absorption anomaly (ECRHEAA), which is the root cause of all global warming, is not linear, but may actually be acceleration, should be a very real cause for concern, for all our world's climate scientists, and all our world's journalists, and all our world's politicians, and us, our whole world population.

(2.4) The distressing upward incremental trend, in the Met Office Hadley Centre HadCRUT5 global surface air temperature anomaly, when compared to an arithmetic series and a quadratic time integral.

HadCRUT5⁷² is the Met Office Hadley Centre (MOHC) dataset, in the historical record, for the global surface air temperature (GSAT)⁷³. We are going to use the HadCRUT5 dataset, for World annual temperature anomalies relative to the pre-industrial period.⁷⁴

I actually learned about this graph from Our World In Data (OWID). Thank you. Their contributors for their graph are: Hannah Ritchie⁷⁵, Pablo Rosado⁷⁶, and Max Roser⁷⁷.

We shall now apply the same analysis in (2.4), as we did in (2.1) and (2.2) and (2.3).

Please try to understand and accept and tolerate, that I have decided to work in milliCelsius (mC). For example, 1.5 Celsius = 1500 milliCelsius, and, 100 milliCelsius = 0.1 Celsius.

For figure 9, we need to derive the annual increment in global surface air temperature, measured in milliCelsius per year, as a natural sequence.

This time, we are not going to do simple linear regression, we are going, to apply an estimated straight line of best fit, with a gentle constant upward gradient, as an approximation to the natural sequence, which will be an arithmetic sequence.

In figure 9, we can see that the arithmetic sequence, is a straight line of best fit, with a very gentle upward gradient. Will this gentle upward gradient be significant ?

For figure 10, we need to go back to, the original HadCRUT5 data graph for global surface air temperature, which we are treating as a natural series, and we are going to apply the arithmetic series and the quadratic time integral, of the arithmetic sequence.

Figure 9. MOHC HadCRUT5. Annual change global surface air temperature (milliCelsius/year).

Maintained by Dr Colin Morice.

Met Office Hadley Centre (MOHC). (<https://www.metoffice.gov.uk/hadobs/hadcrut5>).

- Annual change global surface air temperature (milliCelsius/year) (mC/y).
- Estimated line of best fit = arithmetic sequence.

Figure 10. MOHC HadCRUT5. Global surface air temperature anomaly (milliCelsius) (mC).

Maintained by Dr Colin Morice.

Met Office Hadley Centre (MOHC). (<https://www.metoffice.gov.uk/hadobs/hadcrut5>).

- Global surface air temperature anomaly (milliCelsius) (mC).
- Arithmetic series summation of estimated line of best fit.
- Quadratic time integral of estimated line of best fit = constant acceleration.

Yes, in figure 10, we can clearly see, that the naturally fluctuating upward trend, in the Met Office Hadley Centre global surface air temperature, does compare to the arithmetic series and the quadratic time integral models, which indicates acceleration, in the increasing global surface air temperature anomaly. I believe this analysis may not have ever been done before by any climate scientist.

The gradient in figure 9,
is the rate of acceleration of the quadratic time integral in figure 10.
We may extrapolate from figures 9 and 10,
that the rate of acceleration of the quadratic time integral of the arithmetic sequence,
is 0.460 milliCelsius per year per year (C/y/y),
which equals 460 microCelsius per year per year (μ C/y/y).

For those who may doubt this fitting of a quadratic curve, demonstrating acceleration,
to the naturally fluctuating HadCRUT5 temperature record:

(2.4.1) In section (2.1), in figure 2, we have seen,
The Global Carbon Budget (GCB) measurements, for cumulative world CO2 emissions,
correctly fit a quadratic time integral, which expresses acceleration.

(2.4.2) In section (2.2), in figure 4, we have seen,
The NOAA GML measurements for cumulative atmospheric carbon dioxide,
also correctly fit a quadratic time integral, which expresses acceleration.

(2.4.3) In section (2.3), in figure 8, we have seen, that the NASA CERES measurements,
for The Earth's cumulative radiant heat energy absorption anomaly (ECRHEAA),
correctly fit a quadratic time integral, which expresses acceleration.

(2.4.4) This acceleration, in (2.4.3), is the root cause,
of the accelerating global surface air temperature (GSAT) anomaly, figure 10, section (2.4).
Accelerating ECRHEAA is the directly proportional root cause of accelerating GSAT.
And, we know this is true, from the science of spatial radiant heat energy, causing,
material kinetic heat energy, which causes material temperature, in section (1.3).

(2.4.5) In Addition, We have now seen:

(1) The annual increment in the huge annual magnitude of our world population demand,
for carbon combustion energy, is actually the cumulative accelerating root cause of:

(2) The acceleration of the GCB cumulative world carbon dioxide emissions,
which is the directly proportional accelerating root cause of:

(3) The acceleration of the NOAA GML accumulating atmospheric carbon dioxide,
which is the directly proportional accelerating root cause of:

(4) The acceleration of the NASA CERES ECRHEAA,
which is the directly proportional accelerating root cause of:

(5) The correlating acceleration of The HadCRUT5 global surface air temperature anomaly.

(2.4.1.6) So, (2.4.5)(1)(2)(3)(4) are four proven, causally related,
directly proportional accelerating phenomena, which are,
the directly proportional cause of the observed accelerating phenomenon (2.4.5)(5),
so this, annual incremental global surface air temperature, is an accelerating phenomenon.

Oh no ! Global surface air temperature, which is the metric that we,
our whole world population, know as, global warming, is accelerating.

This news, that global warming is accelerating, may be a complete distressing concern,
for all our world's climate scientists, and our whole IPCC,
and our 2025 Brazil COP30 Climate Conference President André Corrêa do Lago⁷⁸,
and all our world's journalists, and all our world's politicians,
and us, our whole world population.

However, all is not lost,
 as soon as we, our whole world population,
 really start to care, and really start to choose,
 to use, less or much less, carbon combustion energy, every day, now and forevermore,
 so that, as soon as our whole world population's huge annual demand,
 for carbon combustion energy, caringly becomes constant,
 is as soon as global warming stops accelerating, but keeps growing constantly,
 and as soon as our whole world population's huge annual demand,
 for carbon combustion energy, actually caringly starts to constantly annually decrease,
 is as soon as global warming continues to grow less and less rapidly, decelerate.

**(2.5) The distressing upward incremental trend,
 in The Met Office Hadley Centre HadSST global sea surface temperature anomaly,
 when compared to an arithmetic series and a quadratic time integral.**

We are now going to do the same analysis in (2.5) as we did in (2.4).
 We are going to use the Met Office Hadley Centre HadSST4⁷⁹ data.
 I actually learned about this graph from The Our World in Data (OWID) Graph,
 for World annual sea surface temperature anomalies relative to the pre-industrial period.⁸⁰
 Thank you to Our World in Data.

In figure 11, we can see that the estimated straight line of best fit,
 is a very gentle upward gradient. Will this very gentle upward gradient be significant ?

Figure 12. MOHC HadSST4. Global sea surface temperature anomaly (milliCelsius).

Maintained by Dr Caroline Sandford.

Met Office Hadley Centre (MOHC). (<https://www.metoffice.gov.uk/hadobs/hadsst4>).

- Global sea surface temperature anomaly (milliCelsius) (mC).
- Arithmetic series summation of estimated line of best fit.
- Quadratic time integral of estimated line of best fit = constant acceleration.

Yes, in figure 12, we can clearly see, that The Met Office Hadley Sea Surface Temperature (GSST), does compare to an arithmetic series and the quadratic time integral models, which indicate constant acceleration, in increasing global sea surface temperature.

We can extrapolate from figures 11 and 12, that the acceleration in the quadratic time integral model, is 0.303 milliCelsius per year per year, which equals 303 microCelsius per year per year ($\mu\text{C}/\text{y}/\text{y}$).

In comparison, the acceleration in increasing Global Surface Air Temperature, approximated to 460 microCelsius per year per year ($\mu\text{C}/\text{y}/\text{y}$).

We can see, the acceleration in GSST is a dampened version of the acceleration in GSAT, because, the heat capacity of water, is much higher than the heat capacity for air.⁸¹

For figure 13, let us directly compare, The Met Office Hadley Centre's HadCRUT5 GSAT with HadSST GSST.

Figure 13. MOHC. Direct comparison of HadCRUT5 with HadSST4 (milliCelsius).

Maintained by Dr Colin Morice and Dr Caroline Sandford.
Met Office Hadley Centre (MOHC). (<https://www.metoffice.gov.uk/hadobs/index.html>).

(2.5.1) In figure 13, we can see that the natural fluctuations and the upward trends, in global surface air temperature and sea surface temperature, are virtually identical, so that we may understand that the atmosphere and the oceans, are subject to, and respond to, the same naturally fluctuating, global warming phenomena:
(1) which is incoming shortwave infrared radiant heat energy from the Sun,
(2) as well as, longwave infrared radiant heat energy, re-transmitted, in all directions, including downwards, back to The Earth, from greenhouse gas molecules in the atmosphere, which have absorbed outgoing longwave infrared radiant heat, from the Earth's land and oceans.

Understanding these combined phenomena in (2.5.1)(1) and (2), as a complete live simultaneous resonating phenomenon, may help us to understand how extreme heat and heat domes happen.

Figure 13 expresses so much historically, its upward trend zigzags, are so characteristically well known and recognisable, and form one of the patterns in 'the fingerprint of anthropogenic global warming'.

To begin to understand these combined greenhouse phenomena (2.5.1)(1) and (2), please see the helpful educational Trenberth Diagrams for The Earth's Energy Budget in:

Kevin Trenberth et al. (2009). "Earth's Global Energy Budget".
Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society (BAMS).
<https://doi.org/10.1175/2008BAMS2634.1>

P L Read et al. (2015). "Global energy budgets and 'Trenberth Diagrams', for the climates of terrestrial and gas giant planets". Quarterly Journal of The Royal Meteorological Society. <https://doi.org/10.1002/qj.2704>

10 April 2017. "What is Earth's Energy Budget ?" Five Questions with a NASA Climate Scientist Dr Norman Loeb. <https://www.nasa.gov/centers-and-facilities/langley/what-is-earths-energy-budget-five-questions-with-a-guy-who-knows>

IPPC AR6 Chapter 7 figure 7.2. <https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/wg1/figures/chapter-7/figure-7-2>

In order to complete this task, please would you all now like to do, for us, the same analysis, for 700m & 2000m ocean heat content⁸² and ocean pH⁸³, please ? Ocean pH is expressing oceans acidification. Yes, from their graphs it looks like they all may be gently accelerating the same. There is also oceans deoxygenation⁸⁴ due to increasing oceans temperature. All these distressing adverse climate change phenomena, are very not nice for all our beautiful conscious marine creatures.

(3.1) Discovery.

I believe, my five analyses in sections (2.1)(2.2)(2.3)(2.4)(2.5), may represent a significant discovery, which may help you, all our UK climate scientists, and all our world's climate scientists, and the public understanding of global warming.

This discovery is based on the recognition and the understanding:

(3.1.1) For the scientific principle, of the difference between:

- (1) Natural sequences of annual increments global warming data.
 - (2) And their natural series (plural) of annually cumulative global warming data.
- Normally only one of this pair of data is available, so it is necessary to calculate the other data.

(3.1.2) For the mathematical principle, to carry out:

- (1) The simple linear regression, or the estimated line of best fit, of the natural sequence.
- (2) The summation of the arithmetic sequences to produce their arithmetic series.
- (3) The quadratic time integrals of the arithmetic sequences.

(3.1.3) That (3.1.2)(1)(2)(3) may correctly mathematically model (3.1.1)(2), thereby demonstrating that (3.1.1)(2) may be in acceleration.

I searched online for 'climate science' and I found this article:

Lijing Cheng, Grant Foster, Zeke Hausfather, Kevin E. Trenberth, and John Abraham. (2022). "Improved Quantification of the Rate of Ocean Warming".⁸⁵ American Meteorological Society. Journal of Climate.

Where, in their figures 1 and 3, they did linear regression, when they needed to know to do the quadratic time integral of the linear regression. Finding this really distressed me, that they may not have understood this.

I feel deeply profoundly concerned, I need to sincerely ask you, all our UK climate scientists, and all our world's climate scientists, may it have been possible, that you all, may have overlooked, these mathematical principles, in all your analyses, & all your climate computer models ?

So that, now, I may be bringing to all your attention, for the first time, for all your understandings, these necessary mathematical principles, which do demonstrate, that currently, in the history of the world, in sections:
(2.1) Cumulative world carbon dioxide emissions, by The Global Carbon Budget (GCB),
(2.2) Cumulative global atmospheric carbon dioxide, measured by The NOAA GML,
(2.3) The Earth's cumulative radiant heat energy anomaly, measured by NASA CERES,
(2.4) The global surface air temperature, measured by the Met Office Hadley Centre,
(2.5) The global sea surface temperature, measured by the Met Office Hadley Centre,
are all five directly proportional causally related accelerating phenomena, which has been demonstrated, because they all share the same proportional acceleration, which may now form a valid part of the empirical evidence⁸⁶, for the necessary 'fingerprint of anthropogenic global warming', which we, our UK BBC Radio 4 listener population, keep hearing in our BBC Radio 4 News.

(3.1.4) Anthropogenic climate change, is caused by, anthropogenic global warming, which we have now shown, in all five cases, to be an accelerating phenomenon:
(1) The huge annual magnitude of our world population demand, for carbon combustion energy, is a linear sequence, of annual incremental quantities,
(2) which, yes, produces a linear sequence, of annual increments in world carbon dioxide emissions, into our finite air atmosphere,
(3) which, however, as we have shown, with Global Carbon Budget Data, figure 2, in section (2.1), then causes, an accelerating cumulative quantity of carbon dioxide, in our finite air atmosphere,
(4) which, is the directly proportional accelerating root cause, of NOAA GML accumulating atmospheric carbon dioxide, figure 4, in section (2.2),
(5) which, is then, the directly proportional accelerating root cause, of the accelerating NASA CERES ECRHEAA, figure 8, in section (2.3),
(6) which is the directly proportional accelerating root cause, of the accelerating, Met Office HadCRUT5 GSAT and HadSST4 GSST, figures 10 and 12, in sections (2.4)(2.5).
(7) and, this whole accelerating sequence, (3.1.4)(1)(2)(3)(4)(5)(6), are 'the primary fingerprint of all accelerating anthropogenic global warming', which itself is 'global warming's fingerprint on anthropogenic climate change', which we, our whole UK population, keep hearing is necessary in all our news services.

Clearly, the news of these significant new understandings, that five important global warming datasets have been demonstrated, to be causally related accelerating phenomena, should be a huge cause for concern, for you, all our UK climate scientists, and all our world's climate scientists, and all our world's journalists, and all our world's politicians, and us, our whole world population.

When we all now take into account, this new model for accelerating global warming, then we may understand, that the vital IPCC Shared Socioeconomic Pathways⁸⁷, SSP1-1.9, SSP1 2.6, SSP2 4.5, yes, are optimistic, which now absolutely depend on us, our world population, actually caring, and actually actively choosing to reduce our demand for carbon energy, every day, now and forevermore.

(3.1.5) I am really hoping that my findings in this article, may be of special interest and concern to all our world's climate scientists, especially:

- (1) Professor Pierre Friedlingstein FRS et al, at The Global Carbon Budget,
- (2) Dr Xin Lan, Dr Pieter Tans, & KW Thoning, at The NOAA Global Monitoring Laboratory,
- (3) Dr Norman Loeb et al, at The NASA CERES Department,
- (4) Dr Colin Morice et al, at The Met Office Hadley Centre.
- (5) Dr John Kennedy et al, including Dr Caroline Sandford, at The Met Office Hadley Centre.

I am hoping that You All may now be encouraged and inspired to work together, now knowing, that all your global warming data, are sequentially causally related, and demonstrated to be accelerating, such that the accelerating phenomenon of (1)'s data, is the directly proportional accelerating root cause the phenomenon of (2)'s data, which is the directly proportional accelerating root cause, of the phenomenon of (3)'s data, which is the directly proportional, accelerating root cause, of the phenomena of (4)'s and (5)'s data. Where the phenomena of (3)'s data, is the origin of all global warming, which is the root cause of all anthropogenic climate change.

(3.2) Reflecting on the public understanding of climate science in the news.

These genuine new understandings, by applying the mathematical model, of comparing natural sequences, to linear arithmetic sequences, then comparing their natural series, with accelerating quadratic time integrals, may help to solve and validate and answer, the reasons, for your, all our UK climate scientists', and all our world's climate scientists', very real concerns, about all your true observations, which describe, global warming appears to be accelerating, as reported to us, the UK population, in our UK news services:

2 June 2025. New Scientist.

The global temperature may be even higher than we thought.

<https://www.newscientist.com/article/2482510-the-global-temperature-may-be-even-higher-than-we-thought>

10 January 2025. Eos.

"Exceptional" Global Warming Spike Continued in 2024.

<https://eos.org/articles/exceptional-global-warming-spike-continued-in-2024>

23 October 2024. NASA.

There is unequivocal evidence, that Earth is warming at an unprecedented rate. Human activity is the principal cause.

<https://science.nasa.gov/climate-change/evidence>

15 August 2024. The Guardian.

'We should have better answers by now':

climate scientists baffled by unexpected pace of heating.

<https://www.theguardian.com/environment/article/2024/aug/15/we-should-have-better-answers-by-now-climate-scientists-baffled-by-unexpected-pace-of-heating>

19 March 2024. NASA Climatologist Dr Gavin Schmidt.

Climate models can't explain 2023's huge heat anomaly - uncharted territory.

<https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-024-00816-z>

8 May 2024. The Guardian.

World's top climate scientists expect global heating to blast past 1.5C target

<https://www.theguardian.com/environment/article/2024/may/08/world-scientists-climate-failure-survey-global-temperature>

18 November 2023. BBC News.

Climate change: Is the world warming faster than expected ?

<https://www.bbc.co.uk/news/science-environment-67360929>

Karina von Schuckmann et al. (2023).

Heat stored in the Earth system 1960–2020: where does the energy go?

<https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-15-1675-2023>

(3.2.1) The answer is, yes, global warming is accelerating, and now you, all our UK climate scientists, and all our world's climate scientists, may understand the mathematics, which correctly demonstrate why.

I hope my work in this study, may be a help and a service, to you all.

Quite possibly, these new understandings, for this mathematical technique:

(1) of recognising that your data has an annual increment natural sequence component, and an annually cumulative natural series component,

(2) of modelling (1) with an arithmetic series, by simple linear regression or by estimation, and its arithmetic series and its quadratic time integrals, may help you, all our climate scientists, to review and revise, all your graphical analyses, and, to more accurately program all your climate models.

(3.3) The genuine need to encourage and inspire us, our whole world population, to really care and really choose to use less or much less carbon combustion energy, through all our world's news services, whom have the privilege of addressing us, our whole world population, every day.

Like I said in my introduction,

I am one of the UK BBC Radio 4 listener population,

I have been listening to BBC Radio 4,

since at least the time of The Paris 2015 COP21 Climate Conference,

and I deeply profoundly care,

about the public understanding of global warming and climate change,

and the very real need to establish true voluntary carbon combustion energy reductions, in us, our whole world population.

For the public understanding of global warming and climate change, please may I ask:

(3.3.1) Please can global warming always be differentiated from, and not conflated with, climate change, please, because:

(1) Global warming, is separate and definite, and is the root cause, of all climate change⁸⁸, as well as, all the distressing adverse effects of climate change⁸⁹, which are indefinite and statistical, but still happen.

(2) The NASA CERES ECRHEAA, is the key metric, for the origin of accelerating Global Atmospheric Warming, which is measured as, accelerating Global Surface Air Temperature (GSAT), and, accelerating Global Oceans Warming, which is measured as accelerating Global Sea Surface Temperature.

(3.3.2) Please can Professor Pierre Friedlingstein's FRS et al's data, in their global carbon budget, for annual fossil fuel emissions, as elemental carbon, which is now currently of the order of 10 giga tonnes of elemental carbon per year, now be regarded as the equivalent of, "the huge annual magnitude, of our world population demand, for carbon combustion energy", in giga tonnes of elemental carbon combusted per year, please ? This data should then be the key public metric, for the root cause of global warming, and, for whether, we, our whole world population, are continually uncaringly increasing our demand for carbon combustion energy, or whether, we, our whole world population, have begun to caringly voluntarily reduce our demand for carbon combustion energy.

(3.3.3) Like I said in my Introduction, I am only one of our UK population, and I am not at university, and I only live a home-life, please may I ask, those of all of you who are reading this article, that if you feel enlightened by my discovery, and you appreciate my work as a service, please could you please possibly nominate me, for The Royal Meteorological Society's Emerging Communicator Award 2025⁹⁰, please ? Submissions close 17 October 2025. Today, as I write, is Monday 22 September 2025.

(3.3.4) This is what I am hoping for most, I wish that you, all our UK climate scientists, and all our world's climate scientists, all of whom I admire and know by name, as some of you are public figures in The UK, because you have spoken to us, our UK population, in our UK news services, including: USA NASA CERES Climate Scientist Dr Norman Loeb, USA NOAA GML Climate Scientist Dr Xin Lan, USA NOAA GML Climate Scientist Dr Pieter Tans, USA Berkley Earth Climate Scientist Dr Robert Rhode⁹¹, USA Climate Scientist Professor Kevin Trenberth⁹², Our IPCC Chair Professor Sir Jim Skea FRSE⁹³, UK Met Office Professor Richard Betts MBE FRMetS⁹⁴, UK Met Office Professor Peter Stott MBE FRMetS⁹⁵, UK Climate Scientist Professor Ed Hawkins MBE FRMetS⁹⁶, UK Royal Meteorological Society Chief Executive Professor Liz Bentley FRMetS⁹⁷, UK Climate Change Committee Professor Piers Forster FRMetS⁹⁸, UK Climate Change Committee Professor Corinne LeQuere CBE FRS, UK Climate Scientist Professor Pierre Friedlingstein FRS, UK Climate Scientist Professor Emily Shuckburgh CBE FRMetS⁹⁹, EU ECMWF Climate Scientist Dr Samantha Burgess¹⁰⁰, EU ECMWF Climate Scientist Dr Carlo Buontempo¹⁰¹, UK Mathematics Professor Hannah Fry HonFREng FIMA FIET¹⁰², UK Glasgow 2021 COP26 President Lord Alok Sharma KCMG¹⁰³, UK Government Special Representative for Climate Rachel Kyte CMG¹⁰⁴, may all now be able to, immediately, and forevermore, perpetually, write and say: (1) to Our Brazil 2025 COP30 Climate Conference President André Corrêa do Lago, (2) to all our world's journalists, (3) to all our world's politicians, (4) to us, our whole UK population, in all our UK news services, (5) and to us, our whole world population, in all our world's news services, this following saying, for the truest principle, to encourage and inspire world population climate action, please:

To encourage and inspire,
world population climate action,
all our world's climate scientists,
really need to begin fairly asking us,
our whole world population,
in all our world's news services:

“Please can we, our whole world population,
please really care, and please really choose,
to use, less or much less, carbon combustion energy,
every day, now and forevermore, please.”

We need to be sure, which populations in our world, do we fairly want to ask the most ?
Clearly, we do not mean to ask the populations of the poorest countries in the world,
who use the least carbon energy per capita¹⁰⁵, in our world.
Clearly, we mean, we, the economically independent populations,
of all the countries in the developed world, who include us all, in the western world,
who freely use the most carbon energy per capita, for so much travel, as a lifestyle choice,
thereby, we, as populations, are causing accelerating global warming.

(3.3.5) For examples.

(1) At Christmas 2024, in the UK,

The RAC predicted there would be 29 millions cars on the roads¹⁰⁶, that is phenomenal.

(2) And, in the last year, on BBC Radio 4 Inside Science,
Earth System Scientist Professor Mark Maslin¹⁰⁷,
sadly, without expressing his own 'fight against climate change',
said, there are 400 planned world airports¹⁰⁸.

Clearly this future will be a disaster for our atmosphere & our climate & our Earth system.

I am not against individual freedoms,
however, the principle we, our whole world population, need to learn is,
yes, we live as individuals and families and communities, but, we also live as populations,
and it is as populations, that we, our whole world population¹⁰⁹,
are causing adverse effects to our whole Planet Earth, our climate and our biosphere.

When there are, tens of millions, and hundreds of millions, and billions, of people,
who all want to freely engage in all forms of carbon combustion energy travel,
then that is a huge problem for our atmosphere and our climate and our Earth system.

(3.3.6) I am really sorry,
it is really critically important, for you, all our UK climate scientists,
when you speak to us, our UK population, in all our UK news services,
and for you, all our world's climate scientists,
when you speak to us, our whole world population, in all our world's news services:

(1) To get beyond saying only the words, "we need to reduce our carbon emissions".
you really need to actually begin to fairly directly ask us, our whole world population,
to please reduce our demand for carbon energy, as a population, beyond the individual,
this is why I have thoughtfully composed this above example saying,
for you to learn and memorise and recite in your important moments in our news
services.

(2) Because, for the last ten years, ever since our Paris 2015 COP21 Climate Conference,
I have certainly observed from listening to BBC Radio 4,
that, so far, all our climate scientists, and all our journalists, and all our politicians,
have explicitly assiduously avoided, ever having to say, in our news services,
that, we, our whole world population, need to reduce our demand for carbon energy,
and the evidence is, for the last 10 years, we, our whole world population,
have been uncaringly increasing, not caringly decreasing,
our annual demand for carbon energy,
so it is not surprising that climate records are being broken nearly every year.

However, do not despair, this year is 2025,
so Net Zero 2050, is still 25 years into the future,
so this year, 2025, is still the most excellent time,
for you, all our UK climate scientists, and all world's climate scientists,
to begin, perpetually asking us, our UK population, in all our UK news services,
and us, our whole world population, in all our world's news services,
to please care and please reduce our world population's demand for carbon energy.

What I would like to ask you all, please, is,
please can you, all our UK climate scientists, and all our world's climate scientists,
please realise, and please recognise, and please make it your own policy,
that all our UK news services, and all our world's news services,
are the means, by which, you all may directly address,
us, our UK population, and us, our whole world population, as populations,
and, to be able to fairly directly ask us, as populations,
to please care, as populations, and please choose, as populations,
to please use, less or much less, carbon energy, as populations, every day, please ?

Doing this, may mean, for us, the whole 1.01 billion population of The Western World,
actually voluntarily, as populations, adapting to travelling less, driving less & flying less,
and living more contentedly in all our homes, and go out for walks from our homes.
It is compatible with sustainable development, for us, the whole population of The West,
to live more contentedly in peace in our own homes.

Please can I appeal to you, all our UK climate scientists,
and all our world's climate scientists, to please appeal,
to our Brazil 2025 COP30 Climate Conference President André Corrêa do Lago,
to please be the first person in the world, to read & memorise & say the above saying,
to us, our world population, in his forthcoming November COP30 Climate Conference,
world news press conference statements, please ?

(3.4) For us, our whole world population.

Please look at these crucially important world maps online:

- (1) Wikipedia. The Western World¹¹⁰.
- (2) Wikipedia. Developed Countries¹¹¹.
- (3) Wikipedia. Developing Countries¹¹².
- (4) Wikipedia. Least Developed Countries¹¹³.
- (5) Wikipedia. The Human Development Index¹¹⁴.
- (6) The Integrated (Food Security) Phase Classification (IPC)¹¹⁵.

According to Worldometer¹¹⁶:

Our world population grew to	8	billion people in November 2022 ¹¹⁷ .
Our world population is now	8.25	billion people in September 2025.
Our world population may grow to	9	billion people by 2037,
Our world population may grow to	10	billion people by 2061 ¹¹⁸ .

The population of The West	is approximately	1,010,600,000	people.
The population of China	is approximately	1,416,096,000	people.
The population of India	is approximately	1,463,865,000	people.
The population of Africa	is approximately	1,549,867,000	people.

For the sake of all beautiful life, including all beautiful green plant life, and all beautiful conscious creatures, and all beautiful conscious people, and our original perfect beautiful peaceful planet Earth, with its beautiful blue sky, and for the sake of our present world, and the future history of the world, we, our whole world population, need to follow the principles, of sustainability¹¹⁹ and sustainable development¹²⁰ and environmentalism¹²¹, which means, that to be safe, as a whole, we, our whole world population, need to limit our world population to 8 to 9 billion people, and we need to reduce our demand all for natural resources, including carbon energy.

Clearly, we, the whole 1.01 billion people population of The Western World, are economically independent, and we live free lives, and we place a huge demand on natural resources, and carbon energy.

I believe, we, the whole population of The Western World, need to take primary responsibility for reducing our demand for natural resources, and actually care, and actually choose to use less of everything, drive less, fly less, heat our homes less, and be more content to live perpetually in our homes, and be deeply profoundly grateful for everything that we have, our architecture for homes and families, our clothes, our water drinks, our mealtimes, our families, our friends, our schools, our employment, our democracies, where the opposition are welcome in our parliaments.

I believe, we, the whole population of The Western World, need to become deeply profoundly compassionate, towards all the populations, in all the countries in the world, who are living with food insecurity, and undeveloped architecture for civilisation.

I believe, we need our whole world population to be kind caring peace-loving people, with an end, to all interhuman, enmity and harm, and, all interstate, enmity and harm, so that there may be, no more, wars, nor armed conflicts, nor murders, in our whole world, ever again, in the whole history of the whole world.

And, I believe, all these educational understandings, need to be fairly said, to us, our whole world population, in all our world's news services.

Figure 14. Our finite air atmosphere.

This scale diagram illustrates that our finite air atmosphere, is only very delicate membrane upon the entire surface, of our original perfect beautiful peaceful planet Earth.

The above reason, is why, our finite air atmosphere, is being adversely affected, by the distressingly huge annual magnitude, of our annually cumulative world carbon dioxide emissions.

The inner blue circle: the diameter of our planet Earth is 12,742 kilometres.

The 1st red circle: 99% of the mass of our atmosphere, is within 32 kilometres, of the surface of our Earth.

The 2nd red circle: 99.99997% of the mass of our atmosphere, is within 100 kilometres, of the surface of our Earth.

By Michael Jenkins.

World oil consumption is 6km³/y & world oil bill is \$3T/y.

https://www.eia.gov/outlooks/steo/report/global_oil.php

<https://www.statista.com/statistics/859133/global-liquid-fuels-consumption-outlook>

Estimated current world oil consumption (WOC):

WOC = 104,000,000 Barrels per Day

Estimated current price of oil (P00) = \$70 per Barrel

Identities.

1 oil barrel = 42 US gallons = 158.9873 litres

[http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Barrel_\(volume\)](http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Barrel_(volume))

:: = therefore

~ = approximately

1d = 1 day

1y = 1 year

365d = 1y

1k = 1 kilo = 1 thousand = 1,000

1M = 1 mega = 1 million = 1,000,000

1G = 1 giga = 1 billion = 1,000,000,000

1T = 1 tera = 1 trillion = 1,000,000,000,000

1B = 1 barrel

1l = 1 litre

1m = 1 metre

1,000 l = 1 kl = 1 m³ = 1 cubic metre

1 (km)³ = (1,000 m)³ = 1 Gm³ = 1 Tl = 1 cubic kilometre

School maths: scalar dimensions conversions calculations.

:: WOC = (104,000,000 B/d) x (158.9873 l/B) = 16.535 Gl/d

:: WOC = 16.535 Mm³/d = ~16.5 million cubic metres per day

:: WOC = (16.535 Mm³/d) x (365 d/y) = 6.04 Gm³/y

:: WOC = 6.04 (km)³/y = ~6 cubic kilometres of oil per year

Therefore, world oil consumption, is of the order of 6 cubic kilometres of oil per year.

That is way too much.

To illustrate, please imagine, one huge candle, with its wick alight, burning, with its flame, which, is standing on the surface of The Earth, with its square base, with its area of 1 square kilometre, with its height of 6 kilometres, above the ground. Then, that huge volume, of that huge candle, is the huge amount of oil, that is being raised from the oil wells under the ground, each and every year, to satisfy our world population's huge annual demand for petrol and diesel and aviation fuel. And, that candle, has its burning wick, which is combusting the oil, of that huge candle, downwards from the top, at the rate of ~16.5 metres per day, which is, ~688 centimetres per hour.

P00 = \$70 / B

:: P00/d = (\$70/B) x (104 MB/d) = ~\$7.3 billion dollars per day

:: P00/y = (\$7.3G/d) x (365d/y) = ~\$2.7 trillion dollars per year

Therefore, uncaring that we, our whole world population, are causing global warming, by our lifestyle choices, to drive as much as we want, and to fly as much as we want, we willingly spend, of the order of ~\$7 billion dollars per day on oil, and of the order of ~\$3 trillion dollars per year on oil.

Just imagine, if our world population reduced our demand for fuel, that would free up a vast amount of money, for nice things, like our families, our friends, our homes, our clothes, our food, and our international charity.

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